

CURVATURE EFFECT ON LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An experimental investigation was performed to study the effect of curvature on low-velocity impact damage in laminated composites. Matrix cracks and delaminations were the primary concern of the study. Flat and cylindrically curved specimens made of T300/976 graphite/epoxy prepregs were tested. Impact experiments were performed by using the impactors with line-nosed and point-nosed heads. The use of line-loading impactors was intended to generate a simplified impact damage pattern from which the damage mechanism could be characterized. The application of point-loading impact was to assess the overall effect of curvature on the types and extent of the impact damage in laminated composites. Based on the study, it was found that structural configuration can significantly affect low-velocity impact damage in composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that low-velocity impact can cause significant internal damage, such as matrix cracks and delaminations, in fiber-reinforced, organic matrix laminated composites. Such damage is very difficult to detect with the naked eye and may depend strongly upon the material properties of each individual ply, ply orientation, and structural configuration. Accordingly, considerable work has been performed in the literature to study impact damage in laminated composites. However, most of the work so far has been focused on impact damage in flat panels [1-5]. Considerably less attention has been given to evaluate the effect of structural configuration on the impact damage.

Since more and more composite structures are made in curved shapes, such as cylinders, pressure vessels, motor cases, rocket boosters, etc., the geometric configuration of the structures could also affect the impact damage in these structures. Unfortunately, so far, there is very limited information available regarding the effect of curvature on the impact damage in composites. Therefore, the major objective of this investigation was to characterize impact damage in curved composites and to evaluate the effect of laminate curvature on low-velocity impact damage.

2. EXPERIMENTS

The impact tester used for the investigation is described in Figure 1. Basically, the apparatus consists of a pressure tank, a precisely fabricated barrel, a high precision timer, optical fiber photoelectric sensors, and supporting fixtures, etc. The major characteristic of the tester different from any existing ones available in the literature is the design of the barrel which has a rectangular cross section so that the impactor can be designed into two parts: a nose and a base. Accordingly, the nose can be designed separately with different shapes (see Figure 2). Therefore, different types of damage patterns can be produced by appropriately selecting the shape of the nose for the impactor.

In this investigation, both line-nose and point-nose impactors were selected for the study as shown in Figure 2. It has been demonstrated previously [6-8] that the line-nose impactor can considerably simplify the impact damage pattern from a complicated three-dimensional to a simple two-dimensional one. The results of the test data were repeatable and consistent [6-8]. One of the major advantages of the line-loading impact test is that the damage can be easily inspected by the naked eye from the sides of the specimens, significantly reducing the time and the number of specimens required to characterize the impact damage. The procedure is simple and much less tedious and time-consuming than the procedures commonly used for characterizing impact damage caused by a point-nose impactor.

Hence, the use of the line-loading impact tests was intended to characterize the basic damage mechanisms and failure modes of curved laminated composites. Meanwhile, the point-loading impact tests were aimed to assess the effect of curvature on the types and the extent of damage in composites resulting from impact.

T300/976 prepregs were used to fabricate both flat and cylindrical panels. Table 1 lists the dimensions, geometries, and ply orientations of the specimens used in the experiments. All the specimens were cured under the same cure cycle used previously [6, 8]. The dimensions of both flat and curved specimens were kept 10.2 cm long and 2.5 cm wide for the line-loading impact tests, and 10.2 cm long and 7.6 cm wide for the point-loading impact tests. An X-radiograph was taken for each of the specimens before impact to examine the internal damage resulting from manufacturing or cutting. No apparent damage was found in any of the specimens. The testing fixtures for the line-loading and point-loading impact tests are schematically described in Figure 3.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Line-Loading Impact

One of the characteristics of the line-loading impact test results is that an impact velocity threshold exists below which no damage appears, but above which significant damage occurs and can be easily visualized from the side of the specimens [6-8]. Accordingly, each specimen can be tested repeatedly at different velocities until damage is detected.

Hence, during this investigation, each specimen was tested repeatedly. After each test, the specimen was unloaded from the fixture and thoroughly inspected by a binocular microscope with 20 times of magnification to determine any damage from the sides of the specimen. X-radiographs were also frequently taken to ensure the eye inspection.

If no damage was found, the specimen would be re-tested at a higher velocity, and then inspected again. The impact velocity that caused the initial damage was then recorded.

The results of the test data of the line-loading specimens are summarized in Table 2. Clearly, an impact velocity threshold exists for all the specimens tested. At each configuration, the impact velocity thresholds of the five tested specimens varied insignificantly, indicating the consistency and repeatability of the tests. A significant reduction of the impact velocity threshold was recorded as the curvature of the specimens increased. For instance, for flat $[0_6/90_6/0_6]$ panels, the impact velocity threshold was averaged to be about 11 m/s; however, a reduction by more than 60 percent of the impact velocity threshold was measured for the same material with a curvature of 0.17 1/cm. The effect of the curvature on the impact velocity threshold is clearly shown in Figure 4. Apparently, curved composite structures can be much more susceptible to transverse low-velocity impact than flat panels.

The typical damage patterns of the test specimens are shown photographically in Figure 5. The side-view photographs illustrate both symmetric and unsymmetric damage patterns observed from the experiments. However, all the damage patterns exhibit a similar phenomenon in which one or a pair of visual matrix cracks appear in the 90 degree ply group inclined in an angle from the loading direction and bridge two delaminations at the upper and lower interfaces of the cracked 90 degree ply group. It was illustrated previously by Chang et al. [6-8] for flat composites that the occurrence of the matrix cracking corresponds to the initial impact damage and the delaminations initiate from the tips of these matrix cracks.

Point-Loading Impact

Point-loading impact tests are much more cumbersome and tedious than the line-loading impact tests, because the damage produced by point-loading is embedded inside the material. Therefore, each specimen after impact must be inspected by X-ray. A tiny hole of diameter 1.0 mm was drilled at the center of the specimen and dye-enhanced X-ray penetrant was poured through the hole. Accordingly, each specimen was only tested once and then X-rayed to determine the extent and the types of internal damage resulting from impact. Therefore, although more specimens were prepared for the point-loading tests, less test data were generated than for line-loading impact.

Table 3 summarizes the test results of the point-loading impact. The impact velocity threshold for each configuration was taken when the impact velocity was high enough to cause the first damage. The impact velocity threshold also occurred in curved panels subjected to point-loading impact. The effect of the curvature on the impact velocity threshold of point-loading is presented in Figure 6. Again, the greater the curvature the specimen has, the more reduction of impact velocity threshold there will be. The trend is similar to the results generated from line-loading impact given in Figure 4. However, the reduction of the impact velocity threshold due to curvature was not as significant from point-loading impact as from line-loading impact.

The effect of curvature on the extent of impact damage resulting from point-loading impact is demonstrated in Figure 7 by X-radiographs taken from tested specimens. Two ply orientations were considered in the comparison. For each ply orientation, the X-radiographs of the flat and curved specimens were taken from the tests corresponding

to the same impact velocity and the same mass of the impactor. Clearly, the damage patterns of the flat and curved specimens are significantly different from each other.

The extent of the dark area similar to a peanut shape indicates the overall size of the delaminations between 0/90 interfaces inside the specimens, and the straight horizontal and vertical lines correspond to matrix cracks in 0 and 90 degree ply groups, respectively. It seems that the delaminations in the cylindrically curved specimens extended much wider along the axial direction (zero curvature) and smaller along the hoop direction (circumferential direction) than that in flat specimens. Apparently, delamination growth in the hoop direction was suppressed by the curvature of the structure, consequently enhancing the growth of the delaminations into the axial direction of the specimen. The overall sizes of the delaminations in cylindrically curved specimens seem to be slightly bigger than those of flat specimens for a given velocity and mass of the impactor.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

An investigation was performed to evaluate the effect of curvature on the damage of laminated composites resulting from low-velocity impact. Based on the study, the following remarks can be made:

- 1). the curvature of structures can significantly reduce the impact energy threshold of composites.
- 2). curvature could significantly affect delamination growth in composites.
- 3). the impact velocity threshold is an important design parameter for screening materials and designing composite structures for better impact resistance.

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Table 1: Test Matrix of Specimen Configurations Used in the Study

Layup	Loading Type	Specimen Dimensions	Number. of specimen		
			Radius = ∞	R = 7.4 cm	R = 5.8 cm
[06/906/06]	Line-Loading	2.5 cmx10.2 cm	5	5	5
[04/903/04/903/04]			5	5	5
[06/906/06]	Line-Loading	7.6cmx10.2 cm	6	6	6
[04/903/04/903/04]			6	6	6

Table 2: Summary of Line-Loading Impact Test Results

Panels		Thickness (cm)	Specimen ID	Damage initiation at V(m/s)	Average *V _{th} (m/s)
Flat (2.5cm x 10.2 cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	11.225	11.18 ** Stnd Dev. 0.15
		0.254	2	11.035	
		0.254	3	11.375	
		0.254	4	11.081	
Curvature = 0	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	12.86	13.2 Stnd Dev. 0.62
		0.254	2	12.55	
		0.254	3	13.72	
		0.254	4	13.80	
Curved (2.5cm x 10.2 cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	5.256	5.41 Stnd Dev. 0.26
		0.254	2	5.791	
		0.254	3	5.292	
		0.254	4	5.552	
		0.254	5	5.148	
Curvature = 0.135 (1/cm)	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	6.405	6.63 Stnd Dev. 0.20
		0.254	2	6.678	
		0.254	3	6.798	
Curved (2.5cm x 10.2cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	3.867	3.80 Stnd Dev. 0.17
		0.254	2	3.549	
		0.254	3	3.912	
		0.254	4	3.883	
Curvature= 0.171 (1/cm)	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	4.972	5.34 Stnd Dev. 0.51
		0.254	2	4.635	
		0.254	3	5.690	
		0.254	4	5.689	
		0.254	5	5.738	

* V_{th} : Impact velocity threshold

** Stnd Dev. : Standard Deviation

Table 3: Summary of Point-Loading Impact Test Results

Panels		Thickness (cm)	Specimen ID	V(m/s)	Damage	* V _{th} (m/s)	
Flat (7.6 cmX 10.2 cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	2.05	No	2.48	
		0.254	2	2.23	No		
		0.254	3	2.27	No		
		0.254	4	2.40	No		
		0.254	5	2.56	Yes		
		0.254	6	3.59	Yes		
	curvature=0 (1/cm)	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	2.731	No	2.95
			0.254	2	2.90	No	
			0.254	3	3.00	Yes	
			0.254	4	3.16	Yes	
			0.254	5	4.06	Yes	
			0.254	6	4.28	Yes	
Curved (7.6 cmX 10.2 cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	1.87	No	2.08	
		0.254	2	2.0	No		
		0.254	3	2.15	Yes		
		0.254	4	2.28	Yes		
		0.254	5	2.72	Yes		
		0.254	6	3.60	Yes		
	curvature = 0.135 (1/cm)	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	2.20	No	2.34
			0.254	2	2.28	No	
			0.254	3	2.41	Yes	
			0.254	4	2.47	Yes	
			0.254	5	2.72	Yes	
			0.254	6	4.30	Yes	
Curved (7.6 cmX 10.2 cm)	[06/906/06]	0.254	1	1.36	No	1.625	
		0.254	2	1.41	No		
		0.254	3	1.57	No		
		0.254	4	1.68	Yes		
		0.254	5	3.55	Yes		
		0.254	6	4.26	Yes		
	curvature = 0.171 (1/cm)	[04/903/04/903/04]	0.254	1	1.91	No	2.0
			0.254	2	1.95	No	
			0.254	3	2.05	Yes	
			0.254	4	2.41	Yes	
			0.254	5	3.14	Yes	
			0.254	6	3.98	Yes	

* V_{th} : Impact velocity threshold

Figure 1. Schematic of the impact test facility.

Figure 2. Description of the impactors used in the study.

Figure 3. Description of the impact test fixtures. Top: curved plate impact test fixture; Below: flat plate impact test fixture.

Figure 4. Effect of curvature on impact velocity threshold of line-loading impact test.

Figure 5. Photographs of the close side-view of possible failure modes of damaged curved specimens resulting from line-loading impact (Mass=4.17 kg/m).

Figure 6. Effect of curvature on impact velocity threshold of point-loading impact test.

Figure 7. X-radiographs of damaged flat and curved specimens, resulting from point-loading impact (Mass=0.16 kg). Comparisons of the damage pattern between the flat and curved specimens.

